

THE CREATING EVALUATION MODEL ON DESIRABLE CHARACTERISTICS OF STUDENT MORALS ACCORDING TO THE PROMOTING EDUCATIONAL ACT FOR NON-FORMAL AND INFORMAL EDUCATION CENTERS

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Abstract:

To develop and promote the evaluation model on desirable attributions of student morals according to the promoting act for non-formal education and informal education systems were the main purposes, to assess the morals of the desirable characteristics to non-formal education and informal education centers with the research and development (R&D) process were assessed. The research administrations were designed in four phases that composed of the corresponding evaluation of morals or the morals of the desirable characteristics and attributions of learners were investigated with the synthesis of documents and interviews with those involved to evaluate the morals of the desirable attributions, which sample consisted of 9 students. To create evaluating form on the desirable moral aspects of learning for non-formal education and informal educational systems' data from the first phase for drafting format and letting determined from the experts to check with the suitability and feasibility techniques that based on the meeting with expert connoisseurship. Then, to trial evaluation model by assessing the desirable characteristics of a moral centers to non-formal education and informal education with a sample of 166 students in three groups from Roi-Et, Kalasin, Maha Sarakham provinces. Finally, to evaluate the evaluation model by assessor's teacher evaluating model was assessed. It has found that: the components of the evaluation model on desirable attributions of student morals consisted of six components, such as; principle and rationale, three moral behavior indicating purposes of component evaluation, evaluating methods, the evaluators, and

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evaluating criteria. The creating the model results were found that; this evaluation model consisted of 9 elements and 40 indicators of students' behavior groups in each semester with the percentage and quality ratings, the IOC valued indicated of 0.92, responsively. Overall, on evaluation desirable moral of the students in three groups that ranged from 2.11 to 2.40 on the rating weight, ranged from 87.03 to 88.06 on percentage, respectively. Suggestions that the evaluation model is provided and developed of suitable, helpful, correct, and helpful to reality for students' abilities to be applied and promoted in real life situations of their morals to their desirable attributions, exactly.

Keywords: evaluation model, desirable attributions, student morals, promoting act, non-formal education, informal education

1. Introduction

In the four last decades, the situation and problems of national at present in Thailand, it is clear by now that all over the country aimed at improving the economic and financial to strengthen the monetary and fiscal policies that following effects from many countries. As a result, the economic development and prosperity to the objects clearly. The direction of development is not sustainable and that covers both people and objects. Because developing countries aimed at economic growth and technological progress, focusing on the equipment quickly. The lack of balance on the psychological development of a moral and good values has caused problems that affect the quality of life in many countries. In nation developments, one of the crucial aspects is quality of human resource. The others are economy, society, politics, industry and education. Those national development factors inevitably depend on various desired characteristics of the nation's citizens.

The nation's citizens thus become one of the most important components of Thai society. Like all other societies, every sectors of a society requires competent citizens. As previously stated, the competent citizens ought to be in good physical and mental health. They should be capable of thinking, performing jobs and solving problems. The most important is that they should be able to act as efficient man power for national advanced prosperity and stability. As for national permanent and sustainable growth, its human resources ought to be competent in moral, emotional, and adversity quotients. Good citizen-ship, as viewed and concerned conducts both in intellectual skills (such as critical thinking) and participatory skills. In Thai student settings, good

citizenship is specially associated with participatory skills mainly in social norms as national traditions, morality, religious practice and having a peaceful and virtuous life.

Living as a part of Thai society is currently experiencing a decline in social morality, ethics is a serious and deteriorating day by day as the corruption in all occupational groups. Aggressiveness in children and young adults hooked, the latest outbreak among children and youth issues, youth crime is increasing more and more, violence and the age of offenders younger. Children caught offending friends (mingling), using the Internet inappropriately, the media does not care about no drugs creative public mind, which reflects the shortcomings of the education system to have lost, what is called socialization process on "Humanity", or there is at least fullness (Ruangsiyanon, 2012). Especially children and youth, this is the future of the nation is experiencing many social problems that threaten children swarmed young students led astray and behavioral deviations and lack of discipline Thai abandoned its values to social and moral issues problems.

Moral sensitivity, the awareness of how our actions affect other people, it involved being aware of the different lines of action and how each line of action affects the parties concerned. It involves knowing cause-consequent chains of events in the real world, and empathy and role-taking abilities. Moral judgment is based on the work of Piaget (1965) and Kohlberg (1984) and involved intuitions about what is fair and moral. It requires adults to make moral judgments about complex human activities. Moral motivation requires a prioritization of moral values over personal values, particularly in professional settings, and moral character requires individuals to act on their moral convictions. In addition, moral judgment training strategies might include the direct teaching of criteria for making professional moral judgments in cases involving informed consent, paternalism or breaches of confidentiality. For this component, reference should be made to the specific descriptions of prescribed actions found in professional codes of ethics. Moral motivation training might include profession-specific service activities, and the study of professional moral exemplars (i.e., exemplary teachers); and moral character training might include strategies for problem solving and conflict resolution among and between children and adults (Bebeau, Rest & Narvaez, 1999).

Education in Thailand is provided mainly by the Thai government through the Ministry of Education from pre-school to senior high school. A free basic education of twelve years is guaranteed by the constitution, and a minimum of nine years' school attendance is mandatory. In 2009, the Ministry of Education announced the extension of a free, mandatory education to fifteen years. Thailand has made commitments to realize

the right to education for all children in the country, as called for under various laws and regulations. The 1999 Education Act guarantees the right of all children, without discrimination, to a quality education. A Cabinet declaration in 2005 reaffirmed the right of all children, including non-Thai children living in Thailand, to receive an education. Furthermore, the government announced the extension of a mandatory free education from 12 years to 15 years in 2009. Access to basic education has been gradually expanded to an increasing number of children. The net enrolment rate for primary school age children (6 to 11 years) increased from 81.4 per cent in 2000 to 90.05 per cent in 2009. Similarly, the net enrolment rate for secondary school age children (12 to 17 years) increased from 55.4 per cent in 2000 to 72.22 per cent in 2009 (UNICHEF, 2016).

The school structure is divided into four key stages: the first three years in elementary school, Prathom (ประถมศึกษา) 1–3, are for age groups 7–9; the second level, Prathom 4 through 6 are for age groups 10–12; the third level, Matthayom (มัธยมศึกษา) 1–3, is for age groups 13–15. The upper secondary level of schooling consists of Matthayom 4–6 for age groups 16–18 and is divided into academic and vocational streams. There are academic upper secondary schools, vocational upper secondary schools and comprehensive schools offering academic and vocational tracks. Students who choose the academic stream usually intend to enter a university. Vocational schools offer programs that prepare students for employment or further studies.

Formal education consists of at least twelve years of basic education, and higher education. Basic education is divided into six years of elementary education and six years of secondary education, the latter being further divided into three years of lower- and upper-secondary levels. Kindergarten levels of pre-elementary education, also part of the basic education level, span 2–3 years depending on the locale, and are variably provided. Non-formal education is also supported by the state. Independent schools contribute significantly to the general education infrastructure.

Non-Formal Education in Thailand plays important roles for the out of school youth and adults. ONFEC has undertaken two types of education: Non-Formal Education and Informal Education. These two types are in congruent. The Education Act of B.E. 2542 (1999) (Office of the Educational Council, 1999) defined these two types of education as follows: Non-formal education shall have flexibility in determining the aims, modalities, management procedures, duration, assessment and evaluation conditional to its completion. The contents and curricula for non-formal education shall be appropriate, respond to the requirements, and meet the needs of individual groups of learners. Office of the Non-Formal Education Commission (ONFEC). There are seven

NFE Divisions at the main office. There are also NFE Centers at the national level. They are for examples, the Centre of Education Technology, the Centre for Distance Education, Informal Education Centre, and Science Centers.

Non-Formal Education Institutes (at regional, provincial, district levels), Regional Non-Formal Education Centers: there are five regional centres: North, South, East, Northeastern, and Central Centre. Each centre serves as a research and development centre for its region. Provincial Non-Formal Education Science Centers, there are twelve Provincial Science Centers provides science education and knowledge for general people, NFE students, and formal schooling target groups. Vocational Training Centre along the Border Areas, there are seven centers along the borderline of the country to provide skills training for the border people can also serve many Royals projects. Non-Formal Education Provincial Centers, there are 175 provincial centers (include Bangkok NFE centres), Non-Formal Education District Centres, there are 895 centers in this type serving as NFE Institutes providing NFE programmes and activities for target learners (mostly youth and adults) besides these types, there are public libraries at provincial, district level in numbering of numbering 845 libraries. The CLCs – Community Learning Centers Service as a centers for conducting lifelong activities for people in the community whereas common place for creating learning opportunities, knowledge transfer, exchange floor for experiences, and technical issues of the local wisdom. Teaching and learning activities in Non-Formal Education (ONFEC) organize literacy class to teach Thai national language in duration 200 hours. (2-3 hours is set for each period). Normally, time and venue are set according to the agreement of learners. It is a teacher-oriented class. In rural area, classes are organized in the evening after work at CLC. In cities or town, classes are organized during the weekends at CLCs. Literacy primer developed by ONFEC will be provided. Content of primer relates to main functional areas of health, environment, basic law, ethical and moral, vocation, national unity, etc. Regional NFE Centres develop functional literacy materials, mostly for people in that region and Provincial NFE Centres also develop reading materials mostly for ethnic minorities in that province. In 2007, ONFEC in cooperation with Thai Army launch literacy programme to increase national security in the sensitive areas along the borderlines. Teachers of literacy classes are NFE CLC teachers. In the remote areas, those teachers staying at CLCs will spend their time to visit villagers. Informal speaking and listening Thai language will be encouraged during their visit and sometimes integrated in community development activities.

Informal education shall enable learners to learn by themselves according to their interests, potentialities, readiness and opportunities available from persons,

society, environment, media, or other sources of knowledge. Educational institutions are authorized to provide any one or all of the three types of education.

The system of Non-Formal Education is generally more flexible than regular programs in terms of objectives, methods of instruction and study duration. The content and the curriculum can be adapted to suit the needs of individual students and is intended for those who do not do well in the school system or who have failed – for whatever reason – to complete formal primary education. The Department of Non-formal and Informal Education offers both general and vocational programs for adults. General programs are offered at the lower and upper secondary level by means of day and evening classes, distance learning (by correspondence and radio), and self-study for external examinations.

Focused on the curricula of the Non-formal education programs for the Basic Education Act 2551 the Ministry of Education has announced that on 18 September BE 2551 is of course the philosophy "was" used in educational philosophy "is" is based on the idea that the needs of each individual is different. But not everyone has the same needs, "Everyone wants to be happy," People are happy when the technical knowledge, social and environmental assimilation will not be happy. The think-sufficient is not enough to be explained by reasons learning philosophy "is" a most important lesson. The teacher will be the only opportunity to encourage students to think problems or needs learning from real data and make decisions based on adequate information. The data is secure academic communities and the environment if student can make the problem go away. The process is terminated if student is not satisfied that the problem persists to begin considering the options again. This process will be terminated when a student is happy and satisfied with the aim to develop the students' ethics and values that are pretty good and can coexist in peace to the basic knowledge for living and learning continuously. Students' abilities to operate in accordance with the livelihood interests are aptitude and kept up with changes in the economy, social and politic.

Students are sat in the Non-formal and informal education systems that are able to live a good life and be able to deal with the social community have happily under the sufficiency economy philosophy for understanding the history of Thailand, which is particularly proud of its language, art, culture, sports, wisdom, Thailand is a good citizen, adherence to the principles of religion, adhering to the lifestyle and the democratic regime of government with the King as head of state. Awareness of conservation and development of natural resources and the environment, and a person of learning of their skills in the pursuit of their knowledge are improved. Accessing the learning resources and integrated knowledge used in the development of self, family,

community, society and nation are evaluated (Bureau of the Non-Formal Education and Informal Education, 2012: 1-2).

In terms of the assessment and evaluation of desirable characteristics or attributions, the moral of the students in each academic year that led to the assessment results are used to develop desirable moral learners in the next semester until the end of the academic year, which showed that the assessment and evaluation of desirable moral of learners for non-formal education and informal education systems by the moral of three groups in 9 morals of 40 behavior metrics. The evaluation indicated that the behavioral indicators and criteria of their desirable moral evaluation of students for non-formal education and informal education systems were evaluated.

Assessment and evaluation of the students' morals of the desirable characteristics of learners, which will mainly focus on the morals of the desirable characteristics of learners, a assessment to be considered a change of behavior from the beginning of the second semester until the end of the semester concluded of the building model, the models primarily focus on testing knowledge rather than creating assessments desirable moral aspects of their learning outcomes was assessed and evaluated of teachers or personnel matters that include of the evaluating model used to evaluate quality of information or to make an accurate score. If the result is reliable of evaluation data are valid and trusted. These will make a reliable conclusion for right effective decision. However, the evaluation of problems relating to the evaluation model is in many respects of an evaluation that is not intended to focus on the content, but asked for some behaviors, don't cover the features that you need to evaluate. As a result, the evaluation results are not able to desiring feature. If the evaluation does not correspond to the desired conclusion or decision shall not deviate of causing the evaluation model does not meet the purpose, don't have a desired feature, don't know what to evaluating goal. Students will act out what they indicate, and suggested that a desired feature using the wrong model. The model used to evaluate many types of observations, interviews and monitoring and so on.

It is imperative to get help teacher to development of knowledge about how to use the model. Creating a planning model to evaluate and evaluate. Interpretation of the assessment and evaluation of the results of the evaluation model can be truly worthy assessment to improve student seriously the spirit of the ethics office at the primary education system. The informal education requirements with the researchers therefore important to develop a model to assess the morals of the desirable characteristics of learners in the centers for non-formal education and informal education. In order to evaluate the development of desirable attributes to the

effectiveness of the moral and select groups to study outside the province Northeast Central bases, such as; Kalasin, Khon Kaen, Maha Sarakham, Roi Et and also why it is important when developing a model to assess the morals of the desirable characteristics to non-formal education and informal education is completely. To apply the area of operations of the Office of Non-Formal Education and Informal Education in 4 groups Province in Upper Northeast region for containing Bueng Kan, Nong Khai, Nong Bua Lamphu and Udon Thani provinces, in three Middle Northeast included of Nakhon Phanom, Mukdahan and Sakon Nakhon provinces, and four Lower Northeast; Chaiyaphum, Nakhon Ratchasima, Buri Ram and Surin Provinces adding of Sisaket province consisting of Amnat Charoen and Ubon Ratchathani, too.

2. Methodology

This research methodology was to evaluating guidelines of the evaluation model on desirable attributions of student morals according to the promoting act for non-formal education and informal education. It is imperative to get help of students' development of their knowledge about how to use the evaluation model for creating a planning model to assess and evaluate. Interpretation of the assessment and evaluation of the results of the evaluation can be truly worthy assessment to improve student seriously the spirit of the ethics office at the primary education system and informal education requirements. The researchers therefore important to develop a evaluation model to assess the morals of the desirable characteristics of learners. In order to evaluate the development of desirable attributes to the effectiveness of the moral and select groups to study outside the province in the Central of Northeastern region in Thailand was selected.

2.1 Research Objectives

The main objectives of this research were to develop a model to assess the morals of the desirable characteristics of learners in the centers of non-formal education and informal education that a particular purpose follows as:

1. To investigate the guidelines' to evaluate the morals of the desirable characteristics of learners according to the promoting act for non-formal education and informal education systems.

2. To create an evaluation model to evaluate the morals of the desirable characteristics of learners according to the promoting act for non-formal education and informal education systems.

3. To trial the evaluation model for evaluating the morals of the desirable characteristics of learners according to the promoting acts for non-formal education and informal education systems.

4. To assess the evaluation model for assessing the morals of the desirable characteristics of learners according to the promoting act for non-formal education and informal education systems.

2.2 Research Procedures

The development of an evaluation model for evaluating the morals of the desirable characteristics of learners according to the promoting act for non-formal education and informal education systems in this research study conducted by the *Research and Development* technique, which is divided into four phases:

2.2.1 Phase 1: Investigations the Morals According to the Promoting Act

In this synthesis of research papers and interviews with educational experts on exit, finding guidelines to build up the evaluation model on desirable attributions of student morals according to the promoting act for non-formal education and informal education system with the research limitation was as following:

A. Scope of Resources

The scope resources to investigate guidelines of the evaluation model on desirable attributions of student morals according to the promoting act for non-formal education and informal education was divided into two major sources.

1. The references from the documents and research to evaluate on desirable characteristics of student morals according to the promoting act for non-formal education and informal education with 18 volume texts.

2. The 9-professional education experts were the qualified experts who were deeply of the knowledge and experience to assess the evaluation model on desirable characteristics of student morals according to the promoting act for non-formal education and informal education were selected by a specific purposive sampling technique.

B. Content Limitations

To analysis, synthesis and evaluation of student morals according to the promoting act for non-formal education and informal education was divided into two issues.

1. What were the elements preliminary indication desirable moral aspects of learning outside formal educational centers?

2. What were the guidelines to build up the evaluation model on desirable characteristics of student morals according to the promoting act for non-formal education and informal education?

2.2.2 Phase 2: The Creating a Valuation Model

Researcher team led the approaches to assess of student morals according to the promoting act for non-formal education and informal education from the first draft. Creation Form an evaluation model of the moral desirable characteristics of the promoting act for non-formal education and informal education in terms of the manual assembly draft form and presented a draft model prepared for the luminaries. Using a technique based on expert meetings (Connoisseurship) to determine the suitability and feasibility of the model and evaluation criteria to assess the extent described as below:

A. Scoping Data Resources

Based on the expert meeting professionals (connoisseurship) composed of expert's desirable moral learners of 3 professionals, 3 assessors and evaluators, and 3 experts representing non-formal education and informal education, including nine professional experts, providingly.

B. Sample Size

The samples brought to trial evaluation criteria include of 40 students who sat at the Non-Formal Education and Informal Education Centers in Roi-Et District with 2 teachers were used.

C. Content Limitations

The draft assessment form desirable moral at the centers of learning formal education and informal education contained with six elements, such as: background and principal, the purpose of the evaluation, indicator and an evaluating the moral behavior, valuational method, evaluation, and evaluation criteria.

D. Variable Limitations

The variable limitations composed of the appropriate forms of evaluation model, the possibility of the evaluation model, and the reliability of the evaluation criteria.

2.2.3 Phase 3: To Trial the Evaluation Model

Designing the evaluation model was to trial the desirable moral aspects for assessing students in the non-formal education and informal education centers.

A. Research Resources

Designing this research resources included of 3 directors in the non-formal education and informal education centers, 47 teachers who teaches at the non-formal education and informal education centers, and 166 students in three groups in Karasin, Roi-Et, and Mahasarakham Non-Formal Education and Informal Education Centers.

B. Content Limitation

The experimental model was to evaluate the evaluation model on desirable characteristics of student morals according to the promoting act for non-formal education and informal education aimed at assessment as an indicator in the model.

C. Research Variable

Focused on the 47 teachers who teach at the non-formal education and informal education centers, and 166 students in three groups in Karasin, Roi-Et, and Mahasarakham Non-Formal Education and Informal Education Centers were evaluated.

2.2.4 Phase 4: Evaluation Method

Using the evaluation model to evaluate the desirable characteristics of student morals according to the promoting act for non-formal education and informal education of the accuracy and usefulness of the evaluation by the scope was assessed

A. The Group Provides Information

The group provides an assessment model to evaluate the desirable characteristics of student morals according to the promoting act for non-formal education and informal education, which sample consisted of 50 students were used for tryout this model, quality in Karasin, Roi-Et, and Mahasarakham Non-Formal Education and Informal Education Centers.

B. Content Research Limitations

The evaluation model on desirable characteristics of student morals according to the promoting act for non-formal education and informal education process, this study focused on the assessment of teacher evaluation model to evaluate on two aspects; accuracy (accuracy) and its benefits (utility). These valuation model desirable moral aspects of the students by questionnaire with 5 rating scale level.

C. Research Variables

The variables studied in this step of the review of teacher evaluation in trials evaluating the accuracy (Accuracy) and its benefits (Utility). Using the assessment and evaluation guidelines to evaluate the desirable morals of students.

3. Results

3.1 The Components of the Evaluation Model

The components of the evaluation model on the desirable characteristics of students' morals according to the promoting act for non-formal education and informal education system consisted of six components, namely: the rationale, the purpose of the assessment, the indicator moral behavior, how to evaluation, the evaluators, and the evaluation criteria.

3.2 The Results of the Creating evaluation Model

The results of the creating evaluations model to assess the evaluation model on desirable characteristics of student morals according to the promoting act for non-formal education and informal education centers was designed to analyze and the results for the IOC between the rate of assessment by the evaluators revealed that of 0.92, indicating that the assessment of quality available (see in Figure 1).

3.3 The Results of the Experimental Evaluation Model

The Results of the experimental evaluation model on desirable characteristics of student morals according to the promoting act for non-formal education and informal education centers in Roi-Et, Maha Sarakham, and Kalasin on three groups which participants were 166 students. Overall assessment desirable moral, the students' responses in the first group was as 2.18 weight rate of 2.5 percent 87.03, in the second group was as 2.11 weight rate of 2.4 percent, 88.06, and the third group was shown of 3.57 weight rate of 4.1 per cent 87.38 is classified as revenue, respectively were classified as the centers operators.

In terms of Non-Formal Education and Informal Education in Roi-Et Centers, the sample consisted of 40 students in 3 groups. Overall assessment desirable moral of the students in in the first group was as 2.18 weight rate of 2.5 percent 87.02, in the second group was as 2.12 weight rate of 2.4 percent, 88.36, and the third group was shown of 3.58 weight rate of 4.1 per cent 88.41 was classified as revenue, respectively.

3.4 The Components of the Evaluation Model

Figure 1: The components of the evaluation model

In Mahasarakham Centers, the sample consisted of 60 students in 3 groups. Overall assessment desirable moral of the students in in the first group was as 2.15 weight rate of 2.5 percent 85.82, in the second group was as 2.12 weight rate of 2.4 percent, 88.39, and the third group was shown of 3.53 weight rate of 4.1 per cent 86.04 was classified as revenue, respectively.

Finally, in Karasin Centers, the sample consisted of 66 students in 3 groups. Overall assessment desirable moral of the students in in the first group was as 2.21 weight rate of 2.5 percent 88.26, in the second group was as 2.10 weight rate of 2.4

percent, 87.44, and the third group was shown of 3.59 weight rate of 4.1 per cent 87.68 was classified as revenue, respectively.

3.5 The Evaluating Results of the Evaluation Model

The evaluation model assesses the evaluation model on desirable characteristics of student morals according to the promoting act for non-formal education and informal education centers. The participants experimental model to evaluate the desirable characteristics of learners moral centers have formed an opinion on the overall assessment of the suitability are situated at the highest level (average mean score as 4.55) and is located at the highest level (average mean score as 4.51).

References

1. Academic Department, Ministry of Education. (2000). *The development of ethical Thailand symposium on ethics*. Bangkok: The religion.
2. Act to Promote Non-Formal Education and Informal Education. (2008). *Government gazette*. Book now at 41 125 pp. 1-10: March 3, 2551.
3. Bebeau, M. J.; Rest, J. R.; & Narvaez, D. (1999). Beyond the promise: A perspective on research in moral education. *Educational Researchers*, 28 (4), 18-26. EJ587024.
4. Burgette, J. E. (2007). *Transformational Leadership and Moral Development: A Study of College Students as Future Leaders*. Retrieved June 20, 2008, from <http://proquest.umi.com>.
5. Department of Education. Education Region 8. (2002). *Teaching communication development kit series 4*. Practice Martial. Reproduce.
6. Golden Treasure Protector. (2008). *I know concepts and theories of education outside the school system*. Bangkok: Chulalongkorn University.
7. Kohlberg, L. (1984). *The psychology of moral development: Essays on moral development*. San Francisco: Harper and Row.
8. Lee, A. K. (2007). The role of television on moral development from the perspective of the young adult. Retrieved July 1, 2008, from <http://proquest.umi.com>.
9. Miller, S., and Bersoff, B. (2008). *Moral development's development*. Retrieved June 16, 2008, from <http://www.hope.edu/academic/psychology/335/webrep/moraldev.html>.

10. Ministry of Education. (2007). *The reform of the Ministry of education: Act to promote non-formal education and informal education*. Fri. BE 2551. Copier Papers.
11. Office of Policy and Strategy, Office of the Secretary of Education. (2014). *The reform of education towards sustainable development*. Bangkok: National Agricultural Cooperative.
12. Office of the Educational Council. (1999). National Educational Act of B.E. 2542 (1999). Retrieved from <http://www.edthai.com/act/index.htm#1>
13. Office of the Education Council. (2007). *Patterns instill moral values and desirable features*. Retrieved from <http://www.onec.go.th> date of December 20, 2557.
14. Piaget, J. (1965). *Moral development and moral education*. Retrieved December 1, 2008. Retrieved from <http://www.tigger.vic.deul-lnucci/MoralEd/overview.html>.
15. Piaget, J. (1965). *The moral judgment of the child*. New York: Free Press.
16. Promotion of National Strength on Moral Ethics and Values and Center. (2005). *Ethics*. Bangkok: National Strength on Moral Ethics and Values and Promotion Center.
17. Religious Affairs Department, Ministry of Culture. (2007). *A review of the project, teachers teach morality in school*. Bangkok: Community Agricultural Cooperatives of Thailand.
18. Royal, C. W. and Baker, S. B. (2005). Effects of a deliberate moral education program on parents of elementary school students. *Journal of Moral Education*. V34 N2: 215-230.
19. Ruangsiyanon, R. (2012). *The synthetic form of the development of Thailand, responsibility and discipline self*. Bangkok: Bangkok teachers.
20. Tangkathananon, K. (2014). *The assessment and evaluation of practical skills*. Bangkok: Chulalongkorn University.
21. The Development of Non-Formal Education. (2004). *The document knowledge management education*. Bangkok: Bangkok Teachers.
22. UNICHEF. (2016). *Thailand education overview: Education in Thailand*. Retrieved from https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Education_in_Thailand

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